

Enhancing AI/ML-Driven Innovations in Aerial Object Detection through VR Synthetic Dataset Generation

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Outline

- Drones
- What is AI & Data
- DyViR Synthetic Dataset Generator
 - Feature Output
 - Multi-Modality
 - Aerial Objects
- How did the datasets perform?
- What's next?

The MAVRC Team

Drones are everywhere

- Commercial, social, industrial, military, etc.
- Safety of aerial objects and surrounding area is crucial
- Tracking can be done using AI

What is Artificial Intelligence (AI)?

- Computers simulating human intelligence
 - “Make a picture”
 - “Summarize this article”
 - “Write this code”
 - “Find Waldo”

How does a human learn?

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The Importance of Data

- Low amounts = bad
- Low variety = bad
- Low quality = bad

What does data look like?

Real-World	Synthetic
+Authenticity and Accuracy -Creation and Curation	+Customization and Control -Realism Gap

What is Synthetic Data?

- Using Virtual Reality (VR), many types of data can be simulated
 - Video
 - Audio
 - Signals
 - Haptic
 - Motion

Summary of Problem

- We need to track aerial objects
- AI needs data on aerial objects
- It is difficult to get data of aerial objects

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How can we produce large amounts of quality
aerial object datasets?

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Introducing DyViR

- A tool for creating synthetic training datasets for ML object detection
- Customizable virtual environment featuring multiple aerial object classes and biomes

**DyViR:
Virtual Reality Generated
Synthetic Training Datasets for AI**

What does DyViR Produce?

- Video
 - Virtual environment as seen through virtual camera
- Annotations (Labeled Data)
 - CSV containing all features for each video frame

Example Dataset

Frame	Time	label	coords	label - detailed	payload	Has Payload	depth (m)	id	Visual Data Format
0	0 sec	N/A	[0.0, 0.0, 0.0, 0.0]	N/A	N/A	N/A	0	N/A	N/A
1	0.02 sec	DRONE	[257.2, 244.2, 26.2]	DRONE: HEX - CLINI	PAYLOAD: GRENAD	TRUE	19.6	1	Optical
1	0.02 sec	DRONE	[411.6, 350.7, 19.9]	DRONE: SWITCHBL	PAYLOAD: MOLOTC	TRUE	39.25	4	Optical
1	0.02 sec	BIRDS	[277.5, 366.5, 53.3]	BIRDS: CROW	PAYLOAD: NONE	FALSE	68.39	5	Optical
1	0.02 sec	AIRPLANE	[153.7, 379.3, 25.0]	AIRPLANE: C130	PAYLOAD: NONE	FALSE	876.81	6	Optical
1	0.02 sec	DRONE	[280.4, 224.3, 29.0]	DRONE: HEX	PAYLOAD: EXPLOS	TRUE	15.45	7	Optical
1	0.02 sec	DRONE	[272.6, 241.4, 62.4]	DRONE: QUAD	PAYLOAD: EXPLOS	TRUE	10.17	8	Optical
1	0.02 sec	HELICOPTER	[222.9, 338.9, 15.8]	HELICOPTER: HELI	PAYLOAD: NONE	FALSE	113.25	10	Optical
2	0.03 sec	DRONE	[256.7, 244.8, 26.4]	DRONE: HEX - CLINI	PAYLOAD: GRENAD	TRUE	19.57	1	Optical
2	0.03 sec	DRONE	[411.7, 350.7, 19.8]	DRONE: SWITCHBL	PAYLOAD: MOLOTC	TRUE	39.25	4	Optical
2	0.03 sec	BIRDS	[277.4, 366.4, 53.5]	BIRDS: CROW	PAYLOAD: NONE	FALSE	68.47	5	Optical
2	0.03 sec	AIRPLANE	[153.7, 379.4, 25.0]	AIRPLANE: C130	PAYLOAD: NONE	FALSE	876.66	6	Optical
2	0.03 sec	DRONE	[281.0, 223.4, 28.5]	DRONE: HEX	PAYLOAD: EXPLOS	TRUE	15.49	7	Optical
2	0.03 sec	DRONE	[270.8, 242.2, 62.6]	DRONE: QUAD	PAYLOAD: EXPLOS	TRUE	10.16	8	Optical
2	0.03 sec	HELICOPTER	[222.8, 339.1, 15.8]	HELICOPTER: HELI	PAYLOAD: NONE	FALSE	113.26	10	Optical
3	0.05 sec	DRONE	[256.3, 245.5, 26.5]	DRONE: HEX - CLINI	PAYLOAD: GRENAD	TRUE	19.54	1	Optical
3	0.05 sec	AIRPLANE	[284.3, 394.8, 21.4]	AIRPLANE: 787	PAYLOAD: NONE	FALSE	920.87	2	Optical
3	0.05 sec	DRONE	[411.9, 350.8, 19.8]	DRONE: SWITCHBL	PAYLOAD: MOLOTC	TRUE	39.26	4	Optical
3	0.05 sec	BIRDS	[277.3, 366.3, 53.6]	BIRDS: CROW	PAYLOAD: NONE	FALSE	68.56	5	Optical
3	0.05 sec	AIRPLANE	[153.6, 379.6, 25.0]	AIRPLANE: C130	PAYLOAD: NONE	FALSE	876.51	6	Optical
3	0.05 sec	DRONE	[281.6, 222.6, 28.6]	DRONE: HEX	PAYLOAD: EXPLOS	TRUE	15.53	7	Optical
3	0.05 sec	DRONE	[268.7, 243.0, 62.9]	DRONE: QUAD	PAYLOAD: EXPLOS	TRUE	10.15	8	Optical
3	0.05 sec	HELICOPTER	[222.7, 339.3, 15.8]	HELICOPTER: HELI	PAYLOAD: NONE	FALSE	113.26	10	Optical

Example Dataset

frame	time	label	coords	label_detailed	depth_meters	intention
400	6.67 sec	DRONE	[262.0, 253.1, 18.9, 7.1]	HEX1 DRONE	26.85	Area Denial
400	6.67 sec	DRONE	[142.1, 347.5, 11.3, 6.0]	SWITCHBLADE DRONE	73.27	Kinetic Kill
400	6.67 sec	DRONE	[64.1, 362.7, 16.2, 7.9]	SWITCHBLADE DRONE	67.72	Recon
400	6.67 sec	DRONE	[62.3, 331.0, 34.8, 12.2]	BAYRAKTART2 DRONE	68.4	Kinetic Kill
400	6.67 sec	DRONE	[259.2, 239.9, 31.8, 10.9]	HEX1 DRONE	14.53	Travel
400	6.67 sec	DRONE	[268.0, 453.6, 34.8, 34.9]	QUAD DRONE	16.19	Recon
401	6.68 sec	DRONE	[262.1, 253.3, 19.0, 7.2]	HEX1 DRONE	26.84	Area Denial
401	6.68 sec	DRONE	[142.0, 347.5, 11.3, 6.0]	SWITCHBLADE DRONE	73.23	Kinetic Kill
401	6.68 sec	DRONE	[64.1, 362.8, 16.2, 7.9]	SWITCHBLADE DRONE	67.83	Recon
401	6.68 sec	DRONE	[61.6, 331.0, 34.8, 12.2]	BAYRAKTART2 DRONE	68.34	Kinetic Kill
401	6.68 sec	DRONE	[259.0, 239.8, 31.8, 11.0]	HEX1 DRONE	14.52	Travel
401	6.68 sec	DRONE	[275.1, 453.6, 35.4, 34.9]	QUAD DRONE	16.21	Recon

Features

Bounding
Boxes

Classification
Hierarchy

Intentions

Multi-Modality

- Simulate multiple sensor modalities
 - Optical
 - Thermal
 - LiDAR/Depth

Modalities

Depth

0 100

1.00

0 1

Thermal

Editor Only

N/A

0° C 212° C

Night Vision

Toggle Night Vision

Record

Aerial Objects

Results

- Trained YOLOv7-tiny model
- 60.4% performance increase using synthetic + real-world vs. only real-world [1]
- Synthetic datasets can be used to **augment** training of object detection models for aerial object detection

[1] Garrett Williams, George D. Lecakes Jr., Amanda Almon, Nikolas Koutsoubis, Kyle Naddeo, Thomas Kiel, Gregory Ditzler, Nidhal C. Bouaynaya, "DyViR: dynamic virtual reality dataset for aerial threat object detection," Proc. SPIE 12529, Synthetic Data for Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning: Tools, Techniques, and Applications, 125290G (13 June 2023); <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2663417>

Future Work

- Aerial Object Payloads
- Further dataset flexibility
- Other industries/applications

Summary

- Drones are everywhere
- AI can track those drones
- AI needs data of drones
- DyViR can produce data of drones

Rowan University

Thank you :)